

LONG TERM FATIGUE DEGRADATION – SUPERPOSITION OF DRY AND WET PROPERTIES

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Keywords: *Environmental Degradation, Fatigue Mastercurve, Interlaminar Shear, Offshore*

ABSTRACT

Composites used offshore in marine applications are often continuously exposed to water, essentially the lifetime of the structure – typically 25 years or more. Design standards require knowledge of all critical mechanical properties at the end of the design lifetime. Obtaining these properties requires extensive test programs of dry and exposed specimens within the envelope of design temperatures.

This article focuses on the interlaminar shear fatigue, a property that is often critical for design. It is shown that the dependence of interlaminar shear fatigue on temperature can be well described by a master curve approach where the shift factor is determined by an Arrhenius approach. The failure mechanisms differ in dry and wet states, interlaminar matrix shear vs. fiber matrix debonding and shear. This leads to a change in activation energy in the Arrhenius equation. A combined master curve for dry and wet specimens can be obtained by a superposition approach using the glass transition temperatures (T_g) for calculating the shift factor between dry and conditioned states of the material. The approach works well as long as the composite is used below its glass transition temperature and constituents are not affected by chemical degradation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites are gaining wider acceptance in demanding applications in the offshore oil and gas industry. An example is a composite pipe with metal flanges at each end. One critical material property is interlaminar shear, because all loads need to be transferred from the composite pipe to the metal flange. If this pipe is located subsea and transports hot oil, some components of the oil may diffuse into the pipe from the inside and some water may diffuse in from the outside. Even though diffusion is typically low and can be slowed down further by liners the properties of the laminate need to be known with oil or water diffused into the laminate at the end of the design life. Obtaining the properties of saturated laminates is a conservative approach from a mechanical performance point of view. All properties relevant for the design need to be obtained at conditions representing the end of design life [1,2]. This paper concentrates on obtaining one property: long-term fatigue of interlaminar shear strength.

Obtaining long-term performance for a design life of 25 years and more requires some kind of accelerated testing [3]. The current approach used by industry is measuring fatigue SN curves under all relevant environmental conditions [1,2]. Data is extrapolated to the number of load cycles that the component is expected to experience during its lifetime. This approach has worked fine, but it requires many tests, it is time consuming and expensive. For example, fatigue performance was measured for a composite at 20°C and at 80°C. A new application has a design temperature envelope from 0°C to 60°C. Using current design praxis it would be required to test the material at 0°C, because this is outside the previously tested temperature envelope. Testing at 60°C would not be required, because using the SN curve obtained at 80°C would be conservative. However, using the proper data of an SN curve at 60°C could possibly allow making a more efficient pipe. If data could be calculated for the different temperatures much testing could be saved and more efficient components could be produced

tailored to the actual application. The same issues reappear when properties saturated with water or hydrocarbons are needed.

This article shows a quantitative relationship of the SN curve with temperature for saturated and dry conditions that could provide the understanding to reduce the test effort.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

All materials described here were glass fiber amine cured epoxy laminates made by vacuum assisted resin infusion. Glass fibers were from 3B and the epoxy was Hexion RIMR135 resin and RIMH137 hardener.

Obtaining interlaminar shear properties is not straightforward. Many methods exist that all have their advantages and disadvantages [4-8]. Most test methods are described and analyzed for static testing, but not for fatigue testing. The Short Beam Shear Test SBS according to ASTM D2344 is probably the most widely used shear test in industry due to its simplicity. The SBS test method was used here for some dry specimens. Unfortunately, it was not suitable for testing specimens saturated with water, because saturation times would have been too long (more than 24 weeks).

The majority of the testing was done with a modified SBS test: a newly developed I beam bend test. An I-beam that was machined from 20 mm thick laminates replaced the beam of the SBS test. Specimen preparation was tedious, but the specimen has only thin sections reducing the saturation time down to 6 weeks [9]. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the test specimen and setup. The test method worked well for testing static interlaminar shear strength [9].

Fig.1. I-beam test (a) specimen geometry and (b) setup.

All fatigue tests were done in bending at an R-ratio of 0.1 and a frequency of 4 Hz. Test temperatures were 20, 40 and 60 °C. The conditioned specimens were immersed in distilled water at 60°C until saturation and then tested at 20, 40 and 60°C in an immersion chamber. Figure 1 also shows the immersion chamber filled with water.

Fig.2. Normalized SN curves.

Fig.3. Master interlaminar SN curve for all test conditions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2 shows normalized fatigue SN curves of the beam bending tests of dry and saturated with water (conditioned) specimens. Normalization was done against the static dry strength. As expected, higher temperatures give worse fatigue performance and conditioned specimens perform worse than dry specimens. The effect of saturation with water is much larger than the effect of temperature. The interlaminar shear fatigue performance of conditioned specimen at 60 °C is severely reduced.

Time-temperature dependence is frequently modeled with an Arrhenius type approach describing a shift factor a_T along the time axis:

$$\log a_T = \log \left(\frac{t_0}{t_1} \right) = \log t_0 - \log t_1 = \frac{-\Delta H}{2.3RT} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

where t and T are time and temperature respectively. R is the universal gas constant and ΔH is the activation energy. Zhurkov and Korsukov developed this further to explain stress rupture (static fatigue) [10]. By replacing time to failure of the stress rupture test with number of cycles to failure Nakada and Miyano found a similar solution to describe the temperature dependence of fatigue by a shift factor a_N [11]:

$$\log a_N = \log \left(\frac{N_0}{N_1} \right) = \log N_0 - \log N_1 = \frac{-\Delta H}{RT} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

This approach gave good agreement for the set of dry samples and for the samples conditioned with water and tested at 20 °C and 40 °C, allowing to create a fatigue master SN curve, as shown in Figure 3. Room temperature data for dry and conditioned samples also agreed well with measurements done on traditional short beam shear tests, showing that the I-beams are suitable for measuring interlaminar shear strength fatigue [12].

The slopes of the dry and conditioned SN curves (see Figure 2) were different. As a result, the activation energies ΔH describing the shift factor for the dry and conditioned samples were different, 73 and 105 kJ respectively. The difference in slope and activation energies was attributed to a change in failure mechanisms. Dry specimens showed interlaminar shear failure of the matrix. Conditioned specimens showed fiber-matrix debonding combined with through-thickness shear failure, see Fig. 4. More details about the differences in failure mechanisms and behavior of the specimens under fatigue testing are described in [13].

Fig.4. Change of failure mechanism between dry and conditioned specimens.

The reason for the change in failure mechanism was attributed to fiber matrix debonding in the conditioned samples, as shown in Figure 5. This debonding could be seen already in samples that never experienced any testing loads, it was simply caused by the uptake of water. The fiber matrix debonding could be due to the stresses caused by the swelling of the epoxy matrix. It could also be due to chemical degradation of the interphase/sizing between the matrix and the fibers [14] or a combination of the two effects.

Fig.5. Finer Matrix (F/M) debonding in specimens saturated with water.

An important effect of water entering the matrix is that the glass transition temperature of the dry material drops from $T_g^{dry} = 360.25$ K to $T_g^{cond} = 315.15$ K for the conditioned material. Considering that polymer properties tend to change relative to T_g an equivalent temperature T^* was defined as:

$$T^* = T \frac{T_g^{dry}}{T_g^{cond}} \quad (3)$$

where T is the test temperature. Note that temperatures must be given in Kelvin when calculating the temperature ratios.

When using this equivalent temperature a shift factor for creating a common master curve for dry and conditioned materials can be found as:

$$\log N - \log N_R = \frac{-\Delta H}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T_R} - \frac{1}{T^*} \right) \quad (4)$$

where N is the number of cycles to failure and the subscript R stands for “reference”. R is the gas constant.

Applying equation 4 to the data gives a common interlaminar shear fatigue curve for all tests, as shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the data fall nicely on one linear SN curve except the conditioned data at 60 °C. At 60 °C (333.15 K) the conditioned samples are actually above their T_g^{cond} , while all other test conditions were below T_g . This shows that the master curve concept reaches its limit when the material passes the glass transition temperature.

Extrapolating the SN curves to long lifetimes of a component of many years requires that the SN curves do not change with time, i.e. it does not make a difference whether N cycles happen within a few months or many years. As long as no chemical degradation of the laminate happens and the changes in properties are only caused by swelling the property changes are in principle reversible and SN curves can be extrapolated to long times. For the glass composite system tested here it was found that the epoxy matrix does not degrade chemically in water except for some non-critical yellowing [15,16]. The fiber matrix interphase is affected by hydrolysis [14], but since the interphase was already debonded in the conditioned samples this effect is probably not getting worse. The glass fibers also suffer from hydrolysis if directly exposed to water [17]. However, if the glass is well protected inside the laminate the effects of hydrolysis should be much reduced. In addition, the interlaminar shear strength is not much influenced by the strength of the fibers. So overall extrapolation of the results found here should be justifiable.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The dependence of interlaminar shear fatigue on temperature can be well described by a master curve approach where the shift factor is determined by an Arrhenius approach.

The activation energy used in the Arrhenius equation was different for dry and wet specimens. The difference was attributed to a change in failure mechanisms, interlaminar matrix shear vs. fiber matrix debonding and shear.

Taking account of the change of the glass transition temperature when the composite matrix is saturated with water allowed establishing one master SN curve that represents dry and wet (conditioned) specimens.

The approach works well as long as the composite is used below its glass transition temperature.

Extrapolating the data to long lifetimes requires no chemical degradation of the constituent materials. All changes in properties are caused by swelling due to the absorbed chemical, in this case water.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is part of the DNV GL led Joint Industry Project “Affordable Composites” with nine industrial partners and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU). The authors would like to express their thanks for the financial support by The Research Council of Norway (Project 245606/E30 in the Petromaks 2 programme).

The authors would like to thank also Mr. Emeric Mialon, for the assistance in the material preparation and testing, Carl-Magnus Midtbø and Børge Holen for the design and preparation of the immersed testing chamber.

REFERENCES

- [1] DNV-OS-C501, “Composite Components” DNVGL Offshore Standard, 2013
- [2] DNVGL-ST-F119, “Thermoplastic Composite Pipes”, DNVGL Standard, 2018.
- [3] Echtermeyer, A. T. Integrating durability in marine composite certification. In *Durability of Composites in a Marine Environment* (pp. 179-194). Springer Netherlands, 2014
- [4] Adams D, Lewis E. Experimental assessment of four composite material shear test methods. 1997
- [5] Olsson R. A survey of test methods for multiaxial and out-of-plane strength of composite laminates. *Compos Sci Technol* 2011;71(6):773–83
- [6] Whitney JM, Browning CE. On short-beam shear tests for composite materials. *Exp Mech* 1985;25(3):294–300.
- [7] Rosselli F, Santare MH. Comparison of the short beam shear (SBS) and interlaminar shear device (ISD) tests. *Compos A Appl Sci Manuf* 1997;28(6):587–94.
- [8] Adams D, Lewis E. Experimental study of three- and four-point shear test specimens. 1995.
- [9] Abedin I. Gagani, Andrey E. Krauklis, Erik Sæter, Nils Petter Vedvik, Andreas T. Echtermeyer, A novel method for testing and determining ILSS for marine and offshore composites, *Composite Structures* (2019) Vol. 220: 431-440
- [10] Zhurkov, S.N. and Korsukov, V.E. *Atomic mechanism of fracture of solid polymers*. *Journal of Polymer Science*, 1974. 12: p. 385-398.
- [11] Nakada, M. and Y. Miyano, Accelerated testing for long-term fatigue strength of various FRP laminates for marine use. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2009. 69(6): p. 805-813.
- [12] Rocha IBCM, et al. Hygrothermal ageing behaviour of a glass/epoxy composite used in wind turbine blades. *Compos Struct* 2017;174(Supplement C):110–22.
- [13] Gagani, A.I., E.P.V. Mialon, and A.T. Echtermeyer, *Immersed interlaminar fatigue of glass fiber epoxy composites using the I-beam method*. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 2019. 119: p. 302-310.
- [14] Krauklis, A.E.; Gagani, A.I.; Echtermeyer, A.T. Long-Term Hydrolytic Degradation of the Sizing-Rich Composite Interphase. *Coatings* (Switzerland), submitted for publication
- [15] Krauklis, A.E.; Echtermeyer, A.T. Mechanism of Yellowing: Carbonyl Formation During Hygrothermal Aging in a Common Amine Epoxy. *Polymers* (Switzerland) 2018, 10(9), 1017-1031. DOI: 10.3390/POLYM10091017.
- [16] Krauklis, A.E.; Gagani, A.I.; Echtermeyer, A.T. Hygrothermal Aging of Amine Epoxy: Reversible Static and Fatigue Properties. *Open Engineering* (Poland) 2018, 8(1), 447-454. DOI: 10.1515/ENG-2018-0050.
- [17] Krauklis, A.E.; Gagani, A.I.; Vegere, K.; Kalnina, I.; Klavins, M.; Echtermeyer, A.T. Dissolution Kinetics of R-Glass Fibres: Influence of Water Acidity, Temperature and Stress Corrosion. *Fibers* (Switzerland) 2019, 7(3), 22-40, in a *Special Issue: Advances in Glass Fibers*. DOI: 10.3390/fib7030022